

Recommendation 21:

Using 'Policy Making 2.0' to meet the public sector need 'Civil servants as a community of change'

Status quo:

There are already a number of platform supporting policy making 2.0 activities platforms running, both governmental ones as well as from private organisations. However, the popularity of these e-participation platforms varies from country to country: Citizen Space; Futurium; Puzzled by Policy; SOLVIT; OurSpace; Agora Voting; kosovakosovo.com (Serbia, Kosovo); OpenKratio; Policy Compass; Sirvo A Mi Pais; FUPOL applications; Better Reykjavik; Gothenburg, Online forum; The Malmö Initiative.

Existing initiatives that support policy making 2.0 already are: European Citizens' Initiative (ECI); Online EU Public Consultations; Petitions to the European Parliament

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

The technological activities conducted to be conducted in the field of policy making 2.0 should focus on pushing forward the state of the art for the following enabling technologies :

- Big data; Opinion mining and sentiment analysis; Visual analytics for collaborative governance; Serious gaming for behavioural change; Linked open government data; Participatory sensing; Block chain; Global System science

Non-technical challenges:

The activities aimed at improving the public value generated by policy making 2.0 solutions will have to be aimed at attaining the following objectives:

- increase the *pro-activeness* of policy making in dealing with societal issue before they reach unmanageable sizes and/or chronic phases,
- improve the *reactiveness* in dealing with unexpected abrupt events,
- *reduce the gap* between expected outcomes and delivered results.
- The main challenge will be in striking the right *balance* in the collaboration between algorithms and humans in the definition of new decision making processes.

Civil servants as a community of change:

It is widely recognized that people, not organisations, drive innovation. This is even more true in the realm of public sector. Thus, it is necessary that the responsibility and the will to drive changes percolates down the hierarchy and become a responsibility at all levels: from top-level management to midlevel managers and front line staff. They must increase their ability to drive change by collaborating more and differently with each other and with end-users such as citizens, businesses and the third sector. Public sector innovation activities must become more embedded structurally, more strategic and more systematic. Sub needs include the need for a flexible public sector and the reflection that authorities need to be more open-minded. To further illustrate through the informants' voices: "Need of an organizational structure that is flexible and adaptable" and "The collaboration between different municipalities is still difficult".

Policy Making 2.0:

*Policy Making 2.0 refers to the adoption of a Web 2.0 approach to the policy cycle composed of four main steps: agenda setting, policy design, policy implementation, monitoring and evaluation. More specifically, the adoption of a more open, bidirectional and discursive approach by government agencies offers interesting opportunities for: i) increasing citizens' participation and engagement, by providing to more groups a voice in discussions of policy development and implementation; ii) promoting transparency and accountability, and reducing corruption; iii) public services co-production, by enabling government agencies and the public to develop and design jointly government services; and iv) exploiting public knowledge and talent in order to develop innovative solutions to the increasingly serious and complex societal.**

*Bertot, J. C., Jaeger, P. T., & Grimes, J. M. (2012). Promoting transparency and accountability through ICTs, social media, and collaborative e-government. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 6(1), 78–91.

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